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Cycling the Change

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Health related evidence based approach to urban/transport planning: an example of green cycling corridors

Davor Kontić¹, David Kocman¹, Rok Novak¹:

¹ Jozef Stefan Institute, Ljubljana, Slovenia

Author email: david.kocman@ijs.si

It is generally considered that cycling or walking to work is a part of a healthy routine. But to make sure the increase in cycling (as a means of commuting) provides the health benefits cycling promises, novel urban planning measures are needed to protect cyclists from polluted air.

While humans can tolerate exposure to air pollution to a certain level, cyclists and pedestrians are faced with elevated exposure levels, due to their presence in the vicinity of motorised traffic corridors. Whether the level of exposure to air pollution is harmful depends broadly on two factors: air pollution concentration, and the level of physical activity of the person breathing. The more physical exertion, the larger is the intake of pollutants and since the cycling is an intensive activity, the breathing rates can be more than 30% higher than during walking.

This paper will show the contribution of implementing the so called “green cycling corridors” in parallel to main traffic corridors in terms of tackling the exposure levels of cyclists and pedestrians to the pollution from motorised transport on an example from Ljubljana, Slovenia.

With the uses of recent advances in personal sensor devices for air pollution and noise in combination with physical activity devices, the principles of impact evaluation will be used to compare both route alternatives. The comparison will be made based on the environmental (air pollution and noise), societal (public perception, awareness, acceptance) and transport indicators (travel times, transport safety).

This research will be carried out under the auspices of H2020 URBANOME project (www.urbanome.eu) with the aim to demonstrate the evidence based urban/transport planning approach in reducing the exposure to urban air pollution to appreciable levels.